

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Screening of [[1-(4-Methyl/chlorophenyl)-1H-tetrazol-5-yl]thio]acetic Acid [N-Substituted-phenyl)methylene]hydrazides

ANIL K. SENGUPTA* and AJAI BHATNAGAR

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

and

S. K. KHAN

Microbiology Department, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 27 October 1986, accepted 7 August 1987

Some tetrazolythioacetic acid hydrazides were synthesised and screened for their antiviral activity against TMV, SRV, PVX and CGMMV and antibacterial activity against *B. pumilus*, *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus* and *M. flavus*.

SEVERAL 1H-tetrazol-5-thiol derivatives have been found to have a wide range of biological properties such as antiviral¹, antibacterial^{2,3}, anti-inflammatory, anthelmintic⁴, hence, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise new tetrazol derivatives possessing chloro, nitro, hydroxy, methoxy and methyl groups.

Title compounds were prepared by the condensation of [[1-(4-methyl/chlorophenyl)-1H-tetrazol-5-yl]thio]acetic acid, hydrazide with appropriate aryl aldehydes and were screened for their antiviral and antibacterial activities.

Experimental

Melting points were determined by open capillary method in electrically heated apparatus and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds were checked by tlc using iodine vapours as visualising agent. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra (CDCl₃ or DMSO-d₆) were done on a Varian EM 360 spectrophotometer using trimethylsilane as internal reference. CH₃/Cl phenyl 1H-tetrazol-5-thiol (1a/b) were prepared by the method of Freund *et al.*^{5,6}.

[[1-(4 Methyl/chloro phenyl)-1H-tetrazol-5-yl]thio]ethyl acetate (2a, b): 4'-Methyl/chlorophenyl-1H-tetrazole-5-thiol (1a/b) (0.1 mol) was refluxed with chloroethyl acetate (0.11 mol) in dry acetone (50 ml) and potassium carbonate (0.15 mol) for 36-40 h maintaining anhydrous conditions. After distilling excess acetone the reaction mixture was poured in crushed ice. The separated solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol: 2a (58%), m.p. 82°, $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 210(S-C), 1 410(SCH₂), 1 625(C=N),

1 680 (C=O) and 2 900 cm⁻¹ (CH); 2b (62%), m.p. 78°.

[[1-(4-Methyl/chloro phenyl)-1H-tetrazol-5-yl]thio]acetic acid hydrazide (3a, b): Compound 2a/b (0.1 mol) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (0.15 mol) in absolute alcohol (25 ml) for 8-10 h. On removing the excessive alcohol, the separated solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol: 3a (66%), m.p. 159°; 3b (70%), m.p. 180°, $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 220 (S-C), 1 400 (SCH₂), 1 620 (C=N), 1 700 (C=O), 2 900 (CH), 3 080 (NH) and 3 200 cm⁻¹ (NH₂).

[[1-(4-Methyl/chlorophenyl)-1H-tetrazol-5-yl]thio]acetic acid [N-substituted-phenyl)methylene]hydrazide (4a, b): A mixture of 3a/b (0.01 mol) and the appropriate aryl aldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 5 to 7 h. The reaction mixture was cooled in an ice-bath after concentrating and the separated solid was filtered and washed with ethanol to give the products 4a and 4b in about 60-80% yield (Table 1): 4a-1 $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 190 (S-C), 1 400 (SCH₂), 1 520 (N=N), 1 640 (C=N), 1 750 (C=O), 2 960 (CH) and 3 200 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (CDCl₃) 9.6 (1H, OH), 9.1 (1H, s, NH), 7.7-7 (9H, m, Ar-H), 4.7 (1H, s, CH) and 2.3 (2H, s, CH₂); 4a (Sl. no. 7) $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 215 (S-C), 1 430 (SCH₂), 1 500 (N=N), 1 600 (C=N), 1 680 (C=O), 2 980 (CH), 3 060 (OH) and 3 090 cm⁻¹ (NH); 4a (Sl. no. 6) $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 230 (S-C), 1 420 (SCH₂), 1 500 (N=N), 1 640 (C=N), 1 670 (C=O), 2 970 (CH), 3 110 (OH) and 3 210 cm⁻¹ (NH); 4b (Sl. no. 5) δ (CDCl₃) 10.0 (1H, OH), 8.03 (1H, s, NH), 7.9-7.2 (7H, m, Ar-H), 4.7 (1H, s, CH), 3.8 (2H, s, CH₂), 1.4 and 2.3 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 0.7 (3H, s, CH₃).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4a AND 4b

Sl. no.	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Nitrogen % : Found/ (Calcd.)
4a-1	Cl	H	H	H	180	72	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₇ SOCl	22.69 (22.55)
4a-2	Cl	H	H	OH	200	70	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₇ SO ₂ Cl	24.28 (24.81)
4a-3	Cl	H	H	Cl	190	65	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₇ SOCl ₂	20.66 (20.58)
4a-4	Cl	H	H	OOCH ₃	175	62	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₇ SO ₂ Cl	21.12 (20.86)
4a-5	Cl	OCH ₃	H	OOCH ₃	142	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₇ SO ₂ Cl	19.84 (19.42)
4a-6	Cl	OH	H	H	175	75	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₇ SO ₂ Cl	24.56 (24.81)
4a-7	Cl	H	OH	OCH ₃	176	72	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₇ SO ₂ Cl	20.85 (20.09)
4a-8	Cl	NO ₂	H	H	170	67	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₇ SO ₂ Cl	24.88 (24.04)
4a-9	Cl	H	NO ₂	H	180	65	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₇ SO ₂ Cl	24.86 (24.04)
4a-10	Cl	H	H	NO ₂	157	70	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₇ SO ₂ Cl	24.59 (24.04)
4b-1	CH ₃	H	H	H	278	80	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₇ SO	23.88 (23.86)
4b-2	OH	H	H	OH	208	78	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₇ SO ₂	22.65 (22.82)
4b-3	OH	H	H	Cl	205	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₇ SOCl	21.77 (21.78)
4b-4	OH	H	H	OOCH ₃	212	68	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₇ SO ₂	22.16 (21.98)
4b-5	OH	OOCH ₃	H	OOCH ₃	162	65	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ N ₇ SO ₂	20.70 (20.38)
4b-6	OH	OH	H	H	215	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₇ SO ₂	23.01 (22.81)
4b-7	OH	H	OH	OOCH ₃	281	75	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₇ SO ₂	21.52 (21.15)
4b-8	OH	H	H	N(OH) ₂	208	70	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ N ₇ SO	24.43 (24.81)
4b-9	OH	H	NO ₂	H	178	64	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₇ SO ₂	24.88 (24.68)
4b-10	CH ₃	H	H	NO ₂	187	66	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₇ SO ₂	25.00 (24.68)

TABLE 2—ANTIVIRAL ACTIVITIES OF COMPOUNDS 4a AND 4b

Compd. Sl. no.	Percentage haemagglutination titre inhibition of RDV	Percent inhibition of plant virus*					
		TMV/ <i>N. glutinosa</i>		PVX/ <i>G. globosa</i>		CGMMV/ <i>O. amaranticolor</i>	
		<i>in vitro</i>	<i>in vivo</i>	<i>in vitro</i>	<i>in vivo</i>	<i>in vitro</i>	<i>in vivo</i>
4a-1	—	42 ^b	36 ^b	46 ^b	32 ^b	47 ^b	40 ^b
4a-2	3.8	—	—	—	—	—	—
4a-3	4.6	49 ^b	31 ^b	40 ^b	28 ^b	53 ^a	49 ^b
4a-4	4.6	49 ^b	38 ^b	39 ^b	32 ^b	58 ^a	50 ^a
4a-5	2.8	—	—	—	—	—	—
4a-6	—	47 ^b	35 ^b	37 ^b	29 ^b	32 ^b	28 ^b
4a-7	4.4	54 ^a	42 ^b	61 ^a	43 ^b	41 ^b	30 ^b
4a-8	—	48 ^b	40 ^a	52 ^a	50 ^a	—	—
4a-9	2.7	—	—	—	—	—	—
4a-10	3.2	34 ^b	38 ^b	23 ^b	39 ^b	—	—
4b-1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
4b-2	4.2	37 ^b	32 ^b	39 ^b	24 ^b	26 ^b	24 ^b
4b-3	4.2	—	—	—	—	—	—
4b-4	3.8	—	—	—	—	—	—
4b-5	4.4	58 ^a	41 ^b	54 ^a	43 ^b	56 ^a	50 ^a
4b-6	1.4	34 ^b	30 ^b	38 ^b	23 ^b	28 ^b	30 ^b
4b-7	—	68 ^a	52 ^a	62 ^a	48 ^b	58 ^a	56 ^a
4b-8	—	54 ^a	47 ^b	60 ^a	52 ^a	50 ^a	43 ^b
4b-9	—	57 ^a	59 ^b	50 ^a	43 ^b	—	—
4b-10	2.6	42 ^b	33 ^b	39 ^b	43 ^b	—	—

 * Data significant at : ^a5 mg ml⁻¹, ^b10 mg ml⁻¹.

Biological activities :

Against animal virus : 14 compounds of the series were tested against Ranikhet disease virus (RDV) in a stationary culture of the choriallantatic membrane of chick embryo (Table 2). The strain of the RDV employed was the same as Babbar and Dhar⁷. Choriocallantoic membrane (CAM) of 10 days chick embryo were taken and the culture prepared following the method of Babbar⁸. The compounds were dissolved in a nutrient fluid and pH adjusted to 7.2. The solutions were then sterilised at 15 lbs pressure for 15–20 min. Two-fold serial dilutions were then made and 1 ml of each dilution

added to each of the test tube containing the CAM culture.

Against plant viruses : Most of the synthesised compounds were tested for their *in vitro* and *in vivo* antiviral activities against Sunhemp rosette viruses (a strain of TMV), cucumber green mottle mosaic virus and potato virus. The culture of these viruses were maintained by successive host inoculation⁹ on *Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*, *Chenopodium amaranticolor* and *Gomphrena globosa* plants, respectively (Table 2).

Antibacterial : All the synthesised compounds were tested for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against *Bacillus pumilus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Mycoccus flavus*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* using agar diffusion technique¹⁰ (Table 3).

TABLE 3—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS 4a AND 4b

Compd. Sl. no.	Mean diameter after 24 h*				
	<i>B. pumilus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>B. cereus</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>M. flavus</i>
4a-1	-	+	+	-	-
4a-2	-	-	-	-	-
4a-3	+	-	+	+	+
4a-4	-	++	+	+	+
4a-5	++	+	++	+	+
4a-6	-	-	-	-	-
4a-7	+	+	+	+	++
4a-8	-	-	-	-	-
4a-9	-	-	-	-	-
4a-10	++	++	++	++	++
4b-1	+	+	+	+	+
4b-2	-	-	-	-	-
4b-3	++	++	++	++	+
4b-4	+	-	+	+	+
4b-5	++	-	++	++	++
4b-6	-	-	-	-	-
4b-7	-	-	-	-	-
4b-8	++	++	++	++	++
4b-9	+	+	++	-	-
4b-10	+	+	+	+	+
Control ^a	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++

*Zone size : (+)=5–8 mm, (++)=8–12 mm, (+++)=12–15 mm, (++++)=>15 mm, (-)=no inhibition.
^aTetracyclin hydrochloride.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to the Head, Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow, for facilities, and to the Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for providing spectral and other analytical assistance. The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

- J. J. YAOUANE, G. STURTZ, J. L. KRAUS, C. O. HASTEL and J. COLIN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1980, 21, 2689.
- A. J. COWPER, R. R. ASTIK and K. A. THAKER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 1087.

SENGUPTA, BHATNAGAR & KHAN : SYNTHESIS AND ANTIMICROBIAL SCREENING *etc.*

3. Sankyo Co. Ltd., Jap. Pat. 80 108 878/1980 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1981, 94, 30774).
4. M. A. ELDAWY, I. CHAABAN and A. S. MEHANNA, *Egypt. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1978, 19, 185.
5. M. FREUND and H. HEMPEL, *Chem. Ber.*, 1895, 28, 74.
6. M. FREUND and A. S. CHANDER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1896, 29, 2491.
7. O. P. BABBAR and M. M. DHAR, *J. Sci. Ind. Res., Sect. C*, 1956, 15, 249.
8. O. P. BABBAR *J. Sci. Ind. Res., Sect. C*, 1961, 20, 216.
9. D. D. MUKHERJEE, S. K. SHUKLA, H. N. VERMA and L. P. AWASTHI, *Acta Pharm Jugosl.* 1981, 31, 151.
10. R. S. VERMA and S. A. IMAM, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1978, 13, 45.